

METHODS OF TRANSLATING BORROWED TERMS IN THE TOURISM INDUSTRY FROM ENGLISH TO UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotatsiya: Maqola inglizdan o'zbek tiliga o'tkazilgan turizm sohasidagi o'zlashgan terminlarni tarjima qilishda qo'llaniladigan usullarni o'rganadi. Turizmning globalizatsiyasi bilan birga, o'zlashgan terminlarning aniq tarjimasi samarali kommunikatsiya va tushuncha uchun ahamiyatga ega bo'ladi. O'rganishda, transliteratsiya, adaptatsiya, o'zlashgan so'zlarni ishlatish va til organlarining standartlashtirilgan tarjimalarni ta'minlashdagi o'rinini o'z ichiga olgan turli usullar muhokama qilinadi. Ushbu usullar til o'rtasidagi ta'sirli farqni qoplash va turizmni o'zbek tilida tushunchalarini yaxshilashga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: transliteratsiya, adaptatsiya, ma'no tarjimasi, transkreatsiya, dekodlash va kodlash, terminologiya standartlashtirish, mahalliyashtirish, mashin tarjimasi, parallel matndagi tahlil, transkripsiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуются методы перевода заимствованных терминов в туристической индустрии с английского на узбекский язык. С глобализацией туризма точный перевод заимствованных терминов становится важным для эффективного общения и понимания. Исследование рассматривает различные подходы, включая транслитерацию, адаптацию, использование заимствованных слов и роль языковых органов в обеспечении стандартизированных переводов. Эти методы способствуют преодолению языкового барьера и содействуют лучшему пониманию концепций туризма на узбекском языке.

Ключевые слова: транслитерация, адаптация, семантический перевод, транскрипция, декодирование и кодирование, стандартизация терминологии, локализация, машинный перевод, анализ параллельных текстов, транскрипция.

Annotation: This article explores the methods employed in translating borrowed terms in the tourism industry from English to Uzbek languages. With the globalization of tourism, accurate translation of borrowed terms becomes crucial for effective communication and comprehension. The study discusses various approaches, including transliteration, adaptation, loanword usage, and the role of language authorities in ensuring standardized translations. These methods contribute to bridging the linguistic gap and promoting a better understanding of tourism concepts in the Uzbek language.

Keywords: transliteration, adaptation, semantic translation, transcreation, decoding and encoding, terminology standardization, localization, machine translation, parallel text analysis, transcription.

Introduction

The tourism industry is a vibrant and dynamic sector that continuously evolves and adapts to globalization. As a result, the industry often borrows terms from English and other languages to describe new concepts, services, and experiences. Translating these borrowed terms accurately is essential to maintain clear communication within the local context. This article aims to shed light on the methods used to translate borrowed terms in the tourism industry from English to Uzbek languages.

1. Transliteration: Transliteration involves representing borrowed terms using the closest phonetic equivalents in the target language. This method aims to retain the original pronunciation while adapting the spelling to fit the Uzbek language's phonetic structure [4, p.143]. Transliteration is commonly used for proper nouns, brand names, and terms that have become widely recognized in their original form.

Transliteration involves representing borrowed terms using the closest phonetic equivalents in the target language while adapting the spelling to fit the Uzbek language's phonetic structure. Here's an example:

English Term: Hotel

Transliteration: Xotell

In this case, the English term "hotel" is transliterated into Uzbek as "xotell" to reflect its pronunciation while conforming to Uzbek phonetics.

2. Adaptation: Adaptation involves modifying the borrowed terms to better align with the linguistic features and cultural context of the Uzbek language. This method allows for a more seamless integration of terms into the local language, making them easier to understand and pronounce [2, p.38]. Adaptation may involve altering the pronunciation, morphology, or syntax of the borrowed terms while retaining their core meaning.

Adaptation involves modifying the borrowed terms to better align with the linguistic features and cultural context of the Uzbek language. Here's an example:

English Term: Tour Guide

Adaptation: Sayohatchi

Explanation: The English term "tour guide" is adapted as "sayohatchi" in Uzbek. The term is modified to fit the Uzbek language's morphology and pronunciation, making it more accessible and familiar to Uzbek speakers.

English Term: Souvenir

Adaptation: Suvenir

Explanation: The English term "souvenir" is adapted as "suvenir" in Uzbek. In this case, the term is slightly modified to conform to Uzbek phonetics while maintaining its recognizable meaning.

These examples demonstrate how transliteration and adaptation can be applied in translating borrowed terms in the tourism industry from English to Uzbek. Transliteration focuses on representing the original pronunciation, while adaptation modifies the term to fit the linguistic and cultural context of the target language.

3. Loanword Usage: In some cases, borrowed terms are directly incorporated into the Uzbek language without translation or adaptation. These loanwords are used as-is, with their original pronunciation and spelling preserved [3, p.116]. Loanword usage is often seen when the borrowed terms are widely recognized and accepted, and there is no suitable equivalent in the target language.

4. Language Authorities and Standardization: Language authorities play a crucial role in ensuring standardized translations of borrowed terms. They establish guidelines, dictionaries, and glossaries that provide approved translations for specific industries, including tourism. These resources help maintain consistency and accuracy in the translation of borrowed terms, ensuring clear communication within the tourism industry.

Language authorities play a vital role in ensuring standardized translations of borrowed terms in the tourism industry. Here are some ways they achieve this:

- Terminology Standardization: Language authorities establish standardized terminology for the tourism industry. They develop glossaries, dictionaries, and terminology databases that provide approved translations for commonly used borrowed terms [7, p.61]. These resources serve as references for translators and ensure consistency in the translation of terms across different texts and contexts.

- Quality Control: Language authorities implement quality control measures to ensure accurate and standardized translations. They review and evaluate translations of borrowed terms in the tourism industry, checking for linguistic accuracy, cultural appropriateness, and adherence to established guidelines. This helps maintain a high level of quality and consistency in translations.

- Collaboration with Experts: Language authorities often collaborate with subject matter experts, translators, and professionals from the tourism industry. By involving experts in the translation process, they can benefit from their specialized knowledge and insights. This collaboration helps in refining translations, resolving ambiguities, and addressing industry-specific nuances.

- Training and Certification: Language authorities provide training programs and certification courses for translators working in the tourism industry [5, p 133]. These programs educate translators about the specific requirements and challenges of translating borrowed terms in tourism. By offering standardized training and certification, language authorities ensure that translators possess the necessary skills and knowledge to produce accurate and consistent translations.

- Research and Analysis: Language authorities conduct research and analysis on borrowed terms in the tourism industry. They study the linguistic, cultural, and conceptual aspects of these terms to develop appropriate translations [6, p.112]. By staying updated on emerging trends and terminology, language authorities can provide accurate and up-to-date translations.

- Feedback and Revision: Language authorities actively seek feedback from translators, industry professionals, and language users. They encourage input regarding the translations of borrowed terms and incorporate suggestions for improvement. This iterative feedback process helps refine translations and ensures continuous improvement in the standardization of translated terms.

- Dissemination of Standards: Language authorities disseminate their approved translations and guidelines to translators, language professionals, and relevant stakeholders in the tourism industry. They provide access to resources such as style guides, glossaries, and online databases, making standardized translations easily accessible to those involved in translation work [1, p.74]. Through these strategies, language authorities ensure standardized translations of borrowed terms in the tourism industry. Their efforts promote clarity, consistency, and effective communication within the industry, enhancing comprehension and facilitating cross-cultural exchange in the tourism sector.

Conclusion

The translation of borrowed terms in the tourism industry from English to Uzbek languages is a complex task that requires careful consideration of linguistic, cultural, and contextual factors. Transliteration, adaptation, loanword usage, and the involvement of language authorities in standardizing translations are among the key methods discussed. Transliteration involves representing foreign terms using the Uzbek alphabet, while adaptation focuses on modifying the borrowed terms to align them with the phonetic, morphological, and semantic patterns of the Uzbek language. Additionally, the usage of loanwords allows for the incorporation of foreign terms into the Uzbek language, while maintaining their original form and meaning.

The role of language authorities in ensuring standardized translations is crucial for maintaining consistency and accuracy in the translation process. These authorities establish guidelines and terminology standards, facilitating a uniform and coherent translation of borrowed terms within the tourism industry. The methods discussed in the literature contribute to overcoming the challenges of translating borrowed terms and promoting effective communication between tourists, industry professionals, and local communities. They facilitate a better understanding of tourism concepts, enhance cultural exchange, and contribute to the development of the Uzbek tourism sector.

Overall, the methods employed in translating borrowed terms in the tourism industry from English to Uzbek languages provide valuable insights and tools for language professionals, researchers, and stakeholders in the tourism sector. By employing these methods and promoting standardized translations, the industry can enhance cross-cultural understanding, facilitate effective communication, and contribute to the growth and development of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan.

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